

Diaspore morphotypes of the Dori's Tuff carpoflora (74.6 Ma; upper Campanian, Jose Creek Formation), New Mexico, USA

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This file contains the morphotype descriptions of diaspores, accompanying the *Science* article “Diversification of angiosperm reproductive strategies predated the end-Cretaceous extinction.” The diaspores are preserved in the upper Campanian Dori's Tuff (DT) flora from the Jose Creek Formation, south-central New Mexico, USA. The Jose Creek Formation consists of conglomerate sandstones and interbedded fine-grained sandstones and mudstones, representing fluvial channel and floodplain deposits, respectively, as well as silicified volcanic tuffs deposited on an alluvial plain to piedmont environment. Over 450 fossil diaspores, preserved as impressions and cast/molds, were collected from the DT layer, a single layer of recrystallized tuff deposit in the lower portion of the Jose Creek Formation. The diaspore specimens have been categorized into 77 morphotypes, described herein.

Dori's Tuff diaspore		Morphotype #	JC-R01
Shape	Obovoidal	# of layers	2
		Diaspore type	Winged
Infructescence/compound	<input type="checkbox"/>	# specimens studied	1

Descriptions

Obovoidal diaspore with three apical wings (basal attachment areas indicated by white arrows).

Diaspore narrowly obovoidal, 4.4 mm long, 2.4 mm wide; three well-pronounced surficial ridges present on the exposed surface.

Wings oblanceolate to spatulate in overall outline; apex not preserved; 8.5–10.5 mm long (minimum), 2.0–2.5 mm wide; attached to the diaspore apically by minor protrusions; 5–6 parallel veins visible.

Morphotype JC-R01. PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0039.01. White arrows indicating the three apical wings. Scale = 5 mm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore		Morphotype #	JC-R02
Shape	Ovoidal	# of layers	2
		Diaspore type	Winged
Infructescence/compound	<input type="checkbox"/>	# specimens studied	1

Description

Two diaspore units dispersed and preserved together.
 Individual ovoidal to ellipsoidal diaspore with a lateral wing; diaspore 2.0 mm long, 1.3 mm wide (N = 2).
 The lateral wing hemicircular to arcuate; attached across the diaspore length; 2–3 bifurcating veins (white arrows).

Morphotype JC-R02. PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0343.01. Scale = 5mm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R03

Shape Circularly lenticular

of layers 2

Diaspore type winged

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 1

Description

Circularly lenticular winged diaspore.

Diaspore located centrally within a circular wing; wing 12.4 mm long, 10.6 mm wide; diaspore 6.0 mm long and wide.

Morphotype JC-R03. UCMP 244125.01. Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R04

Shape Obovately laminar

of layers 1

Diaspore type winged

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 27

Descriptions

Obovately laminar, thin diaspore; 3.0 mm long (N = 27, s.d. = 0.37), 2.3 mm wide (N = 27, s.d. = 0.42); 2–3 apical projections (white arrows); the thin laminar diaspore probably wind-dispersed.

Morphotype JC-R04. UCMP 244268.01. Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R05

Shape Ovoidal/spheroidal

of layers 1

Diaspore type

Fleshy

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied

1

Descriptions

Infructescence with helically arranged, laterally born diaspores without distinct pedicellate tissues. Preserved peduncle 14.4 mm long, 0.65 mm thick. Five diaspores borne on peduncle.

Individual diaspores with one layer; ovoidal, ellipsoidal, or obovoidal; moderately to highly compressed; 2.0 mm long (N = 5, s.d. = 0.30), 1.5 mm wide (N = 5, s.d. = 0.33).

Morphotype JC-R05. PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0041.01. Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R06

Shape Circularly lenticular

of layers

2

Diaspore type

Fleshy

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied

2

Descriptions

Circularly lenticular to discoid diaspore with two layers.

Outer layer highly compressed; 6.2 mm long, 5.9 mm wide (N = 2); representing ~30% of full diaspore diameter.

Inner layer circularly lenticular to discoid; moderately to highly compressed; 4.4 mm long, 4.1 mm wide (N = 2).

Morphotype JC-R06. UCMP 244572.01.
Scale = 5 mm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore		Morphotype #	JC-R07
Shape	Lacrimoid	# of layers	2
		Diaspore type	Fleshy
Infructescence/compound	<input type="checkbox"/>	# specimens studied	4

Descriptions

Lacrimoid, radially asymmetrical diaspores with two layers.
 Outer layer 10.3 mm long (N = 4, s.d. = 0.90), 5.5 mm wide (N = 4, s.d. = 0.69); length to width ratio >2; outer layer 10–15% of the full diaspore diameter; with surficial wrinkles (A), likely due to taphonomic shrinkage of fleshy tissue; preserved as void space in some parts.
 Inner layer nearly isometric; moderately compressed; 8.0 mm long (N = 3, s.d. = 1.12), 4.8 mm wide (N = 3, s.d. = 0.50).

Morphotype JC-R07. A) PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0346.01. B) UCMP 244299.01, 02. Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore		Morphotype #	JC-R08
Shape	Ellipsoidal	# of layers	2
		Diaspore type	Fleshy
Infructescence/compound	<input type="checkbox"/>	# specimens studied	29

Descriptions

Ellipsoidal to obovoidal diaspore with two layers. Outer layer 25.0 mm long (N = 21, s.d. = 3.60), 13.67 mm wide (N = 21, s.d. = 2.71); highly compressed; surface with patches of small oval protrusions (B–D, white arrows), possibly herbivory damage (DT74). Inner layer ovoidal to ellipsoidal, radially asymmetrical surface smooth and moderately compressed; 17.67 mm long (N = 11, s.d. = 1.51), 10.78 mm wide (N = 11, s.d. = 1.59). Diaspores frequently preserved together in high abundance (6–17 specimens).

Morphotype JC-R08. A) PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0344.01-17. B) PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0100.01. C) PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0102.01. D) PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0102.05. Small, irregularly localized protrusions, likely representing herbivory traces, on the outer layer (white arrows). Scale = 1cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R09

Shape Spheroidal

of layers 1

Diaspore type fleshy

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 31

Descriptions

Spheroidal/globular, moderately to highly compressed diaspore with a single layer. Five longitudinal surficial grooves present; diaspores 13.8 mm long (N = 31, s.d. = 2.74), 12.8 mm long (N = 31, s.d. = 2.70). Specimens compressed in various positions: dorsiventrally (A–D), laterally (E), or positioned in between (F). Some specimens have five obovate tepaloid impressions (C–D, white arrow).

Remarks: It is possible that this morphotype represents a five-loculed capsule fruit, in which case the morphotype would not represent a diaspore. However, there is no specimen showing evidence of dehiscence and there are no cross-sectional specimens showing internal septae, thus this morphotype is interpreted as a diaspore.

Morphotype JC-R09. A. UCMP 244112.01. B) UCMP 244247.01. C) UCMP 244197.01. D) UCMP 245118.05. E) UCMP 245035.01. F) UCMP 244412.01. Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R10

Shape Ovoidal

of layers 2

Diaspore type fleshy

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 1

Descriptions

Ovoidal, highly compressed diaspore with two layers. Outer layer 10.3 mm long, 6.7 mm wide (N = 1). Inner layers ovoid to ellipsoidal; 1.0 mm long (N = 33, s.d. = 0.14), 0.6 mm wide (N = 33, s.d. = 0.10); unevenly distributed within the diaspore.

Remarks. The specimen is interpreted as fleshy diaspores with two layers, instead of a seed with papillate ornamentation because of the irregular shapes and distributions of the ellipsoidal bodies.

Morphotype JC-R10. UCMF 245057.01. Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R11

Shape Ellipsoidal

of layers 2

Diaspore type fleshy

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 2

Descriptions

Ellipsoidal, highly compressed diaspore with two layers.

Outer layer ellipsoidal; 9.7 mm long, 7.4 mm wide (N = 1); representing ~30% of the full diaspore diameter; visible at the broken point (white arrow) between the inner and outer layers.

Inner layer ovoidal to ellipsoidal; 7.5 mm long, 4.8 mm wide (N = 2); reticulate surficial ornamentation with each polygon 0.7–1.5 mm long, 0.5–0.9 mm wide.

Morphotype JC-R11. A) UCMP 244654.01; the outer layer visible at the broken point (white arrow). B) UCMP 244664.01; preserving only the inner layer. Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R12

Shape Obovoidal

of layers 2

Diaspore type fleshy

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 7

Descriptions

Obovoidal, moderately to highly compressed diaspore with two layers.

Outer layer obovoidal to lacrimoid with a linear to slightly convex outline; highly compressed; 11.9 mm long (N = 7, s.d. = 3.22), 8.2 mm wide (N = 7, s.d. = 2.50); maximum width occurring at the distal 60–80% of the diaspore length; distal half of the outer layer surrounding the inner layer representing 10–15% of the full diaspore diameter.

Inner layer spheroidal; moderately compressed; located at the distal half of the diaspore; 6.9 mm long (N = 7, s.d. = 2.04), 6.5 mm wide (N = 7, s.d. = 2.02).

Morphotype JC-R12.

A) UCMP 244436.01.

B) UCMP 245161.01.

C) UCMP 245273.01.

D) PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0353.01-02.

Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore		Morphotype #	JC-R13
Shape	Obovoidal	# of layers	2
		Diaspore type	fleshy
Infructescence/compound	<input type="checkbox"/>	# specimens studied	4

Descriptions

Obovoidal, highly compressed diaspore with two layers.
 Outer layer obovoidal; with a thickened receptacle (A–B) and a thin additional tissue surrounding, but not fully enclosing, the entire diaspore (seen in broken layers, white arrows); 8.2 mm long (N = 4, s.d. = 0.80), 5.7 mm wide (N = 4, s.d. = 0.11); maximum width occurring at distal 70–80% of the diaspore length; receptacle 2.3 mm long, 2.7 mm wide.
 Multiple inner layer, with a minimum number of 6 (gray arrows); ovoidal; 1.6 mm long (N = 9, s.d. = 0.14), 1.2 mm wide (N = 9, s.d. = 0.09).

Morphotype JC-R13. A) UCMP 244469.05. B) UCMP 244441.01. C) PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0122.01. Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R14

Shape Reniform

of layers 2

Diaspore type Fleshy

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 1

Descriptions

Reniform, minimally compressed diaspore with two layers.

Outer layer 24.0 mm long, 12.4 mm wide (N = 1; measured from an incomplete specimen); incompletely preserved (white arrows showing patches of preserved layer); representing ~30% of the full diaspore diameter; narrowly arcuate surficial structures present adjacent to the inner layer (gray arrow).

Inner layer reniform, with polar ends forming ~145°; 20.7 mm long, 10.9 mm wide; radial surficial ridges emerging from one polar end.

Morphotype JC-R14. UCMP 244104.01. Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore		Morphotype #	JC-R15
Shape	Spheroidal	# of layers	2
		Diaspore type	fleshy
Infructescence/compound	<input type="checkbox"/>	# specimens studied	12

Descriptions

Spheroidal, moderately to highly compressed diaspore with two layers.
 Outer layer 11.4 mm long (N = 12, s.d. = 2.46), 10.5 mm wide (N = 12, s.d. = 1.91); layer 1.0–1.8 mm thick, representing 20–25% of the full diaspore diameter; highly compressed; coriaceous.
 Inner layer spheroidal; moderately compressed; 8.7 mm long (N = 12, s.d. = 1.95), 7.9 mm wide (N = 12, s.d. = 1.59).

Morphotype JC-R15. A) UCMP 245116.01. B) UCMP 244131.01. C) PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0114.01. Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R16

Shape Spheroidal

of layers 2

Diaspore type Fleshy

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 16

Descriptions

Spheroidal diaspore with two layers.

Outer layer spheroidal; highly compressed; 7.5 mm long (N = 16, s.d. = 1.16), 6.7 mm wide (N = 16, s.d. = 1.05); layer 0.4–0.8 mm thick, representing 10–15% of the full diaspore diameter, thickness uniform across the diaspore.

Inner layer 6.3 mm long (N = 16, s.d. = 1.12), 5.6 mm wide (N = 16, s.d. = 0.89); moderately compressed.

cf. JC-R15: JC-R16 is distinguished by the overall small size and relatively thinner outer layer.

Morphotype JC-R16. A) UCMP 244144.01. B) UCMP 245247.01. C) UCMP 244407.01.

Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R17

Shape Spheroidal/ellipsoidal

of layers 2

Diaspore type Fleshy

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 2

Descriptions

Spheroidal to ellipsoidal, moderately compressed diaspore with two layers. Outer layer spheroidal to ellipsoidal; 7.6 mm long, 6.8 mm wide (N = 2); layer representing 30–40% of the full diaspore diameter; broken off at the median line of the inner layer, showing a distal and asymmetrical position of the inner layer within the diaspore.

Inner layer elliptically lenticular; distally located within the diaspore; 5.3 mm long, 4.2 mm wide (N = 2); minimally compressed.

Morphotype JC-R17. A) PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0098.01. B) UCMP 244954.01. Scale = 5 mm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore		Morphotype #	JC-R18
Shape	Spheroidal	# of layers	2
		Diaspore type	Fleshy
Infructescence/compound	<input type="checkbox"/>	# specimens studied	2

Descriptions

Spheroidal, highly compressed diaspore with two layers.
 Outer layer spheroidal; highly compressed; 3.0 mm long, 2.7 mm wide (N = 2); layer 0.3–0.4 mm thick, representing 25–30% of the full diaspore diameter.
 Inner layer spheroidal; centrally positioned; moderately compressed; 2.2 mm long, 2.0 mm wide (N = 2).
 cf. JC-R15: JC-R18 is nearly isometric; however, the dimensions are over 1/3 of those of JC-R15, and there are no specimens of intermediate dimensions, therefore the specimens are described as a separate morphotype.

Morphotype JC-R18. PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0348.01-02. Scale = 1 mm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R19

Shape

of layers

Diaspore type

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied

Descriptions

Obovoidal to ellipsoidal diaspore with two layers.

Outer layer obovoidal with convexly tapering outline; 9.9 mm long, 5.5 mm wide (N = 1); length to width ration ~ 1.8 ; layer 0.2–0.4 mm thick, representing $\sim 5\%$ of the diaspore diameter in areas where the outer layer is in contact with the inner layer.

Inner layer obovoidal with convexly tapering outline; minimally compressed; surface smooth; filling distal 85% of the diaspore length; 8.3 mm long, 5.2 mm wide (N = 1).

Morphotype JC-R19. UCMP 244097.01.

Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R20

Shape Spheroidal

of layers 2

Diaspore type fleshy

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 3

Descriptions

Spheroidal, highly compressed diaspore with two layers.

Outer layer highly compressed; 4.3 mm long (N = 3, s.d. = 0.40), 4.1 mm wide (N = 3, s.d. = 0.23); representing 30–45% of the full diaspore diameter.

Inner layer circularly lenticular to discoid, with two concentric lenticular to discoid structures connected by 8–10, evenly spaced radial projections; outer circle 4.1–4.4 mm long, 3.9–4.6 mm wide (N = 2); inner circle 2.6–2.8 mm long, 2.3–2.8 mm wide (N = 2); projections 0.3–0.4 mm thick.

Position of the inner layer within the diaspores is variable, likely due to preservational distortion of the fleshy outer layer.

Morphotype JC-R20. A) UCMP 245018.01, 03. B) UCMP 244126.01. Scale = 5 mm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R21

Shape Obovoidal

of layers 2

Diaspore type fleshy

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 1

Descriptions

Obovoidal to ellipsoidal diaspore with two layers.

Outer layer 16.6 mm long, 13.7 mm wide (N = 1); layer of uniform thickness in preserved parts (2.0–2.2 mm; white arrows), representing 25–35% of the full diaspore diameter; dimensions measured from conservatively extrapolated outline, extending the uniform thickness of the patchily preserved outer layer.

Inner layer obovoidal; 13.7 mm long, 13.0 mm wide (N = 1); 5–6 longitudinal surficial ridges on the exposed surface.

Morphotype JC-R21. UCMP 244543.01.
Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R22

Shape: Pyriform/obovoidal

of layers: 1

Diaspore type: fleshy

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied: 1

Descriptions

Pyriform to obovoidal, highly compressed diaspore with a single layer; with thickened pedicellate tissue; 15.1 mm long (10.6 mm long excluding the pedicellate tissue), 9.9 mm wide (N = 1); pedicel 4.8 mm long, 3.2 mm wide; surface heavily wrinkled, likely due to taphonomic shrinkage of fleshy tissues; stylar end with a circular, plug-like tissue (white arrow); thickened pedicel interpreted as a part of the diaspore.

Morphotype JC-R22. UCMP 244127.01.
Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R23

Shape Spheroidal

of layers 2

Diaspore type Fleshy

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 14

Descriptions

Pedicellate, spheroidal, minimally to moderately compressed diaspore with two layers. Pedicel 5–7 mm long, 1–1.5 mm wide; 4–5 narrowly triangular tepals with acuminate tips adpressed to the diaspore.

Outer layer spheroidal to ellipsoidal; 5.5 mm long (N = 14, s.d. = 0.74), 5.2 mm wide (N = 14, s.d. = 0.95); layer 0.8–1.4 mm thick, representing 35–50% of the diaspore diameter.

Inner layer spheroidal; located centrally within the diaspore; 3.6 mm long, 3.1 mm wide (N = 1); visible in one specimen that is cross-sectionally broken off (A, white arrow).

Morphotype JC-R23. A) UCMP 244103.01-04. B) UCMP 245055.01-07. C) UCMP 244102.01-03. Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R24

Shape Ellipsoidal

of layers 1

Diaspore type fleshy

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 3

Descriptions

Pedicellate, highly compressed diaspores with retained tepaloid lobes.

Pedicel 1.7–2.0 mm long, 0.4–0.5 mm wide. 2–3 tepaloid lobes visible on the exposed surface (A-B, white arrows); lobes triangular; 0.6–0.9 mm long; 0.3–0.4 mm wide at the base.

Diaspore ellipsoidal to ovoidal; 1.9 mm long (N = 5, s.d. = 0.39), 1.4 mm wide (N = 5, s.d. = 0.23); apical styler notch present (gray arrows); pronounced 10–12 longitudinal furrows present (A, gray arrows).

Morphotype JC-R24. A) PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0108.01. B) PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0091.02. C) UCMP 245190.01. Scale = 5 mm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R25

Shape Fusiform

of layers 2

Diaspore type fleshy

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 1

Descriptions

Pedicellate, ovoidal to conical diaspore with two layers.

Outer layer surrounding the inner layer conical, together with a thickened pedicellate tissue forming an overall fusiform shape; 9.1 mm long, 5.7 mm wide (N = 1); thickened pedicellate tissue 1.4 mm long, 2.2 mm thick in the most thickened region.

Inner layer ovoidal to lacrimoid; 5.8 mm long, 4.0 mm wide.

Morphotype JC-R25. PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0342.01. Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R26

Shape Obovoidal/ellipsoidal

of layers 2

Diaspore type fleshy

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 1

Descriptions

Pedicellate, ellipsoid to obovoid fleshy diaspore with two layers.

Pedicle thick; interpreted as a part of the diaspore; 7.4 mm long, 3.5 mm wide.

Outer layer obovoidal to ellipsoidal; 22.3 mm long, 11.5 mm wide; of uneven thickness surrounding the apically located inner layer; layer 2.0–4.8 mm thick.

Inner layer ellipsoidal; located in the apical 50% of the diaspore; highly compressed and preserved as carbonized materials; 10.6 mm long, 8.4 mm wide.

Morphotype JC-R26. UCMP 244107.01. Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R27

Shape Ellipsoidal

of layers 1

Diaspore type Fleshy

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 1

Descriptions

Ellipsoidal, highly compressed diaspore with one layer; 9.3 mm long, 7.4 mm wide (N = 1); length to width ratio ~1.25.

Morphotype JC-R27. UCMP 244665.01. Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R28

Shape Ellipsoidal

of layers 1

Diaspore type Fleshy

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 1

Descriptions

Obovoidal, likely compound diaspore with two layers. The diaspore outline (outer layer) defined by multiple inner layer, each surrounded by highly compressed, likely fleshy tissue; the diaspore thus likely represent a compound fruit.

Outer layer obovoidal; highly compressed; 4.1 mm long, 2.4 mm wide (N = 1).

Inner layer minimum 7 in number (7 discernable structures visible on the exposed surface); 1.2 mm long (N = 7; s.d. = 0.11), 0.9 mm wide (N = 7, s.d. = 0.08).

Morphotype JC-R28. PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0110.02. Scale = 5 mm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R29

Shape Pyriform

of layers 1

Diaspore type Fleshy

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 1

Descriptions

Pyriform, highly compressed diaspore with one layer; 14.4 mm long, 7.7 mm wide (N = 1); maximum width occurring at 70% of the length.

Morphotype JC-R29. UCMP 244516.01.
Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R30

Shape Ovoidal

of layers 1

Diaspore type Fleshy

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 1

Descriptions

Ovoidal to spheroidal diaspore with two layers, with inner and outer layer in contact basally.

Outer layer ovoidal; preserved entirely as a void space; 1.3 mm long, 1.4 mm wide (N = 1).

Inner layer spheroidal; basally connected to the outer layer; 0.8 mm long, 1.0 mm wide (N = 1).

Morphotype JC-R30. PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0341.03. Scale = 1 mm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore		Morphotype #	JC-R31
Shape	Ovoidal/ellipsoidal	# of layers	1
		Diaspore type	Other
Infructescence/compound	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	# specimens studied	6

Descriptions

A terminal order infructescence with pedicellate diaspores.
 Individual diaspores ellipsoidal; moderately compressed; 2.3 mm long (N = 17, s.d. = 0.28), 1.7 mm wide (N = 17, s.d. = 0.30); 3–5 longitudinal ridges present on the exposed surface.
 Pedicel 0.2–0.4 mm wide; ridged; 60–70% thicker towards the base of diaspore, pedicel <25% of the diaspore thickness at the widest (cf. JC-R32).
 Three to four diaspores in different developmental stages, indicated by size, showing acropetal development.

Morphotype JC-R31. A) PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0109.01. B) PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0356.01. C) UCMP 244882.03. Scale = 5 mm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore		Morphotype #	JC-R32
Shape	Ellipsoidal/spheroidal	# of layers	1
		Diaspore type	Other
Infructescence/compound	<input type="checkbox"/>	# specimens studied	2

Descriptions

Either a terminal segment of an inflorescence or pedicellate diaspores born on the same axis.
 Individual diaspores ellipsoidal, 2.0 mm long (N = 4 , s.d. = 0.39), 1.4 mm wide (N = 4 , s.d. = 0.10).
 cf. JC-R31: individual diaspore with smooth surface; borne on a stout pedicel that are 30–60% of the diaspore width at the base of the diaspore (compared to <25% in JC-R31); pedicels <50% in diaspore length.

Morphotype JC-R32. A) PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0095.04. B) UCMP 244517.01. Scale = 5 mm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R33

Shape Ellipsoidal

of layers 1

Diaspore type Other

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 1

Descriptions

Ellipsoidal, minimally compressed diaspore with a single layer; a prominent longitudinal ridge present across the length, polar end grading into pronounced ridges, representing ~10% of the full diaspore diameter; Diaspore 6.8 mm long, 4.1 mm wide (N = 1).

Morphotype JC-R33. PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0097.01. Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R34

Shape: Rhomboidally lenticular

of layers: 1

Diaspore type

Other

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied

10

Descriptions

Rhomboidally lenticular, single-layered diaspore with two prominent longitudinal ridge; 2.44 mm long (N = 10, s.d. = 0.37), 1.72 mm wide (N = 10, s.d. = 0.34); length to width ratio ~2.5.

cf. The characteristics are similar to the winged morphotype JC-R01 without the wings; however, the dimensions are much smaller in JC-R34 and no protruding wing attachment areas visible as in JC-R01.

Morphotype JC-R34.

A) PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0087.07.

B) PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0353.03a-f.

C) PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0128.06-07.

Scale = 5 mm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R35

Shape Spheroidal

of layers 2

Diaspore type Other

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 5

Descriptions

Spheroidal, moderately compressed diaspore with two layers.

Outer layer with a single conical projection; 4.1 mm long (N = 5, s.d. = 0.81), 3.6 mm wide (N = 5, s.d. = 0.91); representing 10–15% of full diaspore diameter.

Inner layer spheroidal; moderately compressed; 3.0 mm long (N = 5, s.d. = 0.72), 2.7 mm wide (N = 5, s.d. = 0.70).

Morphotype JC-R35. A) PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0156.04. B) PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0341.01. C) PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0120.01. D) UCMP 244501.01,02. Scale = 5 mm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R36

Shape Lenticular

of layers 2

Diaspore type Other

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 12

Descriptions

Ovately lenticular diaspore with two layers.

Outer layer asymmetrical; one end in contact with the inner layer, and the opposite end tapering into a projection; thin and laminar compared to the inner layer; 10–12 parabolic surficial ridges present, with each curve branching and anastomosing, sometimes forming irregular reticulate patches (D); 5.2 mm long (N = 12, s.d. = 0.52), 3.6 mm wide (N = 12, s.d. = 0.36).

Inner layer ovoidal; 3.7 mm long (N = 9, s.d. = 0.64), 2.5 mm wide (N = 9, s.d. = 0.31).

Among the 12 specimens, nine specimens show distinct inner and outer layer (e.g., A–B), whereas three specimens do not show distinct layers (e.g., C–D); in the former, the inner layer dimensions were used as diaspore size as the outer layer is thin and laminar, and the latter case the outer layer dimensions are used as diaspore size.

Morphotype JC-R36. A) UCMP 244526.01. B) UCMP 244527.01. C) UCMP 244069.07. D) UCMP 244069.05. Scale = 5 mm

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R37

Shape Ovately lenticular

of layers 2

Diaspore type Fleshy

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 7

Descriptions

Ovately to trapezoidally lenticular diaspore with two layers.
Outer layer 5.1 mm long (N = 7, s.d. = 0.39), 4.1 mm wide (N = 7, s.d. = 0.43); coriaceous; 20–40% of the full diaspore diameter.
Inner layer ovate to trapezoidal in outline; bilobed, with two longitudinally elongate concave parts; 3.9 mm long (N = 7, s.d. = 0.38), 2.9 mm wide (N = 7, s.d. = 0.26); outermost zone showing palisade structure (B, white arrow).

Morphotype JC-R37. A) UCMP 244528.01-05. B) UCMP 244656.01. Scale = 5 mm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R38

Shape Ovoidal

of layers 1

Diaspore type Other

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 1

Descriptions

Ovoidal, highly compressed diaspore with one layer; 9.2 mm long, 6.4 mm wide (N = 1); distal 80% showing densely packed polygonal surficial pits; individual pits 0.5–0.9 mm in diameter.

Morphotype JC-R38. UCMP 244975.01.
Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R39

Shape Conical

of layers 2

Diaspore type Other

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 1

Descriptions

Conical diaspore with two layers, maximum width at one polar end, linearly tapering into the opposite end.

Outer layer 8.7 mm long, 5.5 mm wide (N = 1); outer layer representing <10% of the full diaspore diameter in preserved parts.

Inner layer conical, minimally compressed, 7.8 mm long, 5.1 mm wide (N = 1),

Morphotype JC-R39. UCMP 245029.01. Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R40

Shape Obovoidal

of layers 1

Diaspore type Other

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 1

Descriptions

Obovoidal, moderately to highly compressed diaspore with one layer, preserved as mold; 15.6 mm long, 8.8 mm wide (N = 1); maximum width occurring at the distal 75% of the length, convexly tapering into both polar ends.

Morphotype JC-R40. PMNS-PAL-06-0116.01. Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R41

Shape Spheroidal

of layers 2

Diaspore type Other

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 1

Descriptions

Spheroidal, pedicellate diaspore with two layers.

Outer layer 7.7 mm long, 7.7 mm wide (N = 1); layer 0.6–1.0 mm wide, representing 25% of the full diaspore diameter; fibrous; pedicel 2.5 mm wide, ~30% of the diaspore width.

Inner layer spheroidal; 6.5 mm long, 6.3 mm wide (N = 1); minimally compressed.

Morphotype JC-R41. UCMP 245117.01. Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R42

Shape Ellipsoidal

of layers 1

Diaspore type Other

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 1

Descriptions

Ellipsoidal, minimally compressed diaspore with one layer; 21.5 mm long, 11.5 mm wide (N = 1); radially asymmetrical with a slight curvature, with polar ends and median point forming $\sim 160^\circ$.

Morphotype JC-R42. UCMP 244415.01. Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R43

Shape Ovoidal?

of layers 1

Diaspore type Other

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 2

Descriptions

Ovoidal (likely; based on the overall morphology of two incomplete specimens), single-layered diaspore with rows of surficial pits; diaspore 3.8 mm long, 2.5 mm wide (minimum dimension, based on a more completely preserved specimen). Circular pits regularly spaced in rows (minimum row number 6); 0.15–0.25 mm in diameter; pits separated by 0.1–0.2 mm gaps.

Morphotype JC-R43. A) UCMP 244497.02, showing minimum dimensions. B) UCMP 244264.01, showing partial imprints. Scale = 5 mm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R44

Shape Narrowly obovoidal

of layers 1

Diaspore type Other

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 1

Descriptions

Narrowly obovoidal diaspore with one layer; 12.2 mm long, 5.4 mm wide (N = 1); length to width ratio >2; three longitudinal ridges visible on the exposed surface; surface with irregularly wrinkled texture.

Morphotype JC-R44. UCMP 244388.01.
Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore		Morphotype #	JC-R45
Shape	Spheroidal	# of layers	2
		Diaspore type	Other
Infructescence/compound	<input type="checkbox"/>	# specimens studied	2

Descriptions

Spheroidal diaspore with two layers.
 Outer layer 13.6 mm long, 11.8 mm wide (N = 2); layer 0.6–1.0 mm thick, representing 10–15% of the diaspore diameter in uniform thickness across the diaspore.
 Inner layer spheroidal; minimally compressed; 11.5 mm long, 10.5 mm wide (N = 2); two circular furrows, joint at a point, visible on the exposed surface.
 Remarks: The two studied specimens are variable in size. The surficial circular furrows are diagnostic to this morphotype and are not found in other spheroidal morphotypes.

Morphotype JC-R45. UCMP 244406.01. Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R46

Shape: Triangularly lenticular

of layers: 2

Diaspore type: Other

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied: 14

Descriptions

Lenticular diaspore with two layers, with an asymmetrically triangular to arcuate outline. Inner and outer layer nearly isometric.

Outer layer 13.9 mm long (N = 14, s.d. = 2.11), 9.4 mm wide (N = 14, s.d. = 1.22); 0.7–1.2 mm thick, representing 15–25% of the full diaspore diameter; nearly uniform in thickness across the diaspore.

Inner layer lenticular, with an asymmetrically triangular to pie-shaped in outline; 10.6 mm long (N = 10, s.d. = 1.73), 7.2 mm wide (N = 10, s.d. = 1.15); longitudinal surficial striation (A, B).

Morphotype JC-R46. A) UCMP 244252.01. B) PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0352.01. C) UCMP 244254.01-07. Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R47

Shape Ovoidal

of layers 2

Diaspore type Other

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 3

Descriptions

Obovoidal, convexly outlined, minimally to slightly compressed diaspore with two layers.

Outer layer ovoidal, convexly tapering into the polar ends; 11.0 mm long (N = 3, s.d. = 0.08), 8.3 mm wide (N = 3, s.d. = 0.43); layer 0.9–1.4 mm thick, representing 10–20% of the full diaspore diameter; nearly uniform in thickness across the diaspore.

Inner layer isometric to the outer layer; 9.2 mm long (N = 3, s.d. = 0.14), 7.1 mm wide (N = 3, s.d. = 0.28).

Remarks: All three studied specimen is preserved as molds.

Morphotype JC-R47. A) UCMP 244515.01. B) UCMP 244662.01. C) UCMP 244125.02. Scale = 1cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore		Morphotype #	JC-R48
Shape	Ovoidal	# of layers	2
		Diaspore type	Other
Infructescence/compound	<input type="checkbox"/>	# specimens studied	3

Descriptions

Obovoidal, convexly outlined, minimally to slightly compressed diaspore with two layers.; inner and outer layer nearly isometric.
 Outer layer ovoidal, convexly tapering to the polar ends; 7.0 mm long (N = 3, s.d. = 0.12), 5.5 mm wide (N = 3, s.d. = 0.34); layer 0.6–0.8 mm thick, representing 10–20% of the full diaspore diameter; uniform in thickness across the diaspore.
 Inner layer isometric to the outer layer; 5.6 mm long (N = 3, s.d. = 0.30), 4.4 mm wide (N = 3, s.d. = 0.28).
 Remarks: All three studied specimen is preserved as molds. The overall morphology and relative ratio of the layers similar to the morphotype JC-R47, but the size distribution of the specimens is nearly bimodal with the JC-R48 specimens nearly half the size of JC-R47, which resulted in the separation of two different morphotypes.

Morphotype JC-R48. A) UCMP 244196.01. B) UCMP 244192.01. C) UCMP 245272.01. Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R49

Shape Ellipsoidal

of layers 2

Diaspore type Other

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 1

Descriptions

Ellipsoidal, convexly outlined, moderately compressed diaspore with two layers; inner and outer layer nearly isometric.

Outer layer ellipsoidal, with a convex outline tapering into the polar ends; 7.0 mm long (N = 3, s.d. = 0.12), 5.5 mm wide (N = 3, s.d. = 0.34); layer 0.1–0.2 mm thick, representing 10–20% of the full diaspore diameter, uniform in thickness across the diaspore; maximum width occurring at 50% of the diaspore length.

Inner layer nearly isometric to the outer layer; 5.6 mm long (N = 3, s.d. = 0.30), 4.4 mm wide (N = 3, s.d. = 0.28).

Morphotype JC-R49. UCMP 244072.01. Scale = 5 mm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R50

Shape Lacrimoid/obovoidal

of layers 2

Diaspore type Other

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 14

Descriptions

Lacrimoid to obovoidal diaspore with two layers.

Outer layer lacrimoidal; 5.7 mm long (N = 14, s.d. = 0.66), 3.2 mm wide (N = 14, s.d. = 0.50); length to width ratio ~ 1.3 ; layer 0.3–0.6 mm thick, representing 20–30% of the diaspore diameter.

Inner layer ellipsoidal, 3.3 mm long (N = 4, s.d. = 0.59), 2.3 mm wide (N = 4, s.d. = 0.36).

Morphotype JC-R50. UCMF 244507.01-13. Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R51

Shape Spheroidal/ovoidal

of layers 1

Diaspore type Other

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 13

Descriptions

Ovoidal to spheroidal, minimally to moderately compressed diaspore with one layer. Diaspore 2.7 mm long (N = 13, s.d. = 0.37), 2.3 mm wide (N = 13, s.d. = 0.24).

Remarks: Morphotypes JC-R51 to -R55 are described based on a single-layered diaspore that are in similar dimensional ratio without distinctive surficial characters. Separation between the morphotypes is based on the overall size: when diaspore length and width are plotted, specimens are discontinuously plotted (D). It is possible that these morphotypes underrepresent the diversity; however, there are no other discernible features to further differentiate such spheroidal/ovoidal/ellipsoidal diaspores with one layer.

Morphotype JC-R51.

A) UCMP 244253.01.

B) UCMP 244129.01.

C) UCMP 244562.01.

D) Differentiation of the morphotypes JC-R51 to -R55, based on diaspore dimensions.

Scale = 5 mm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore		Morphotype #	JC-R52
Shape	Spheroidal/ovoidal	# of layers	1
		Diaspore type	Other
Infructescence/compound	<input type="checkbox"/>	# specimens studied	32

Descriptions

Spheroidal to ovoidal, minimally to moderately compressed diaspore with one layer.
 Diaspore 4.5 mm long (N = 40, s.d. = 0.50), 3.8 mm wide (N = 40, s.d. = 0.58).

Morphotype JC-R52. A) UCMP 244508.05-06. B) UCMP 245043.01. C) UCMP 245289.01. D) UCMP 244662.01. Scale = 5 mm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R53

Shape Ovoidal

of layers 1

Diaspore type Other

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 2

Descriptions

Ovoidal, moderately compressed diaspore with one layer; 7.5 mm long, 6.2 mm wide (N = 2); length to width ratio ~1.2.

Morphotype JC-R53. A) UCMP 245093.01. B) UCMP 244434.01. Scale = 5 mm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R54

Shape Ellipsoidal

of layers 1

Diaspore type Other

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 1

Descriptions

Ellipsoidal, minimally compressed diaspore with one layer; 10.9 mm long, 8.9 mm wide, 6.5 mm thick (N = 1); diaspore nearly uncompressed, with the exposed dimensions allowing measurement of length, width, and thickness.

Morphotype JC-R54. UCMP 244505.01. Scale = 10 mm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore		Morphotype #	JC-R55
Shape	Spheroidal/ovoidal	# of layers	1
		Diaspore type	Other
Infructescence/compound	<input type="checkbox"/>	# specimens studied	2

Descriptions

Spheroidal to ovoidal, moderately compressed diaspore with one layer; 1.5 mm long, ¼ mm wide (N = 2).

Morphotype JC-R55. A) UCMP 244129.02. B) UCMP 244970.04. Scale = 1 mm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R56

Shape Obovoidal

of layers 1

Diaspore type Other

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 2

Descriptions

Obovoid diaspore with one layer; 8.5 mm long, 5.4 mm wide (N = 2); irregularly distributed, elliptic surficial pits present; individual pits 1.0–1.3 mm long, 0.6–0.9 mm wide.

Morphotype JC-R56. A) UCMP 244982.01. B) UCMP 244193.01. Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R57

Shape Triangularly lenticular

of layers 1

Diaspore type Other

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 1

Descriptions

Triangularly lenticular diaspore with one layer; 5.5 mm long, 4.7 mm wide; reticulate surficial ridges ~0.25 mm thick; individual irregularly polygonal cells 0.67–1.17 mm long, 0.51–0.79 mm wide.

Morphotype JC-R57. UCMP 244522.01. Scale = 5 mm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R58

Shape Ovoidal/lacrimoid

of layers 1

Diaspore type Other

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 2

Descriptions

Broadly obovoid to lacrimoid, moderately compressed diaspore with a single layer; outline linearly tapering towards the apical end; 9.4 mm long, 7.9 mm long (N = 2); length to width ratio ~ 1.2 ; maximum length occurring at $\sim 25\%$ of the length.

Morphotype JC-R58. UCMP 244531.01.
Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore		Morphotype #	JC-R59
Shape	Ovoidal/lacrimoid	# of layers	1
		Diaspore type	Other
Infructescence/compound	<input type="checkbox"/>	# specimens studied	2

Descriptions

Ovoidal to lacrimoid, minimally to moderately compressed diaspore with a single layer; 8.1 mm long, 5.6 mm long (N = 2); length to width ratio ~1.5; 3–4 evenly spaced longitudinal furrows present on the exposed surface.

Morphotype JC-R59. A) UCMP 244523.01. B) UCMP 244509.01. Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore		Morphotype #	JC-R60
Shape	Obovoidal	# of layers	1
		Diaspore type	Other
Infructescence/compound	<input type="checkbox"/>	# specimens studied	2

Descriptions

Ovoidal to triangularly lenticular, moderately compressed diaspore with one layer; 9.6 mm long, 6.8 mm wide (N = 2); length to width ratio 1.3–1.5; outline asymmetrically triangular to oval, convexly tapering.

Morphotype JC-R60. A) UCMP 244311.03. B) UCMP 244311.04. Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore		Morphotype #	JC-R61
Shape	Elliptically lenticular	# of layers	1
		Diaspore type	Other
Infructescence/compound	<input type="checkbox"/>	# specimens studied	6

Descriptions

Elliptically lenticular diaspore with one layer; 7.2 mm long (N = 6, s.d. = 1.31), 5.8 mm wide (N = 6, s.d. = 1.21).
 cf. JC-R06 (lenticular diaspore with two layers): the dimension of present morphotype is larger than the fleshy outer layer of JC-R06.
 cf. JC-R52 (obovoidal to spheroidal diaspore with one layer): highly compressed JC-R52 can resemble the present morphotype; however, the dimension is much larger in the present morphotype.

Morphotype JC-R61. A) UCMP 245044.01. B) UCMP 245041.01. C) UCMP 244433.01. Scale = 5 mm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R62

Shape Ellipsoidal

of layers 2

Diaspore type Other

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 1

Descriptions

Ellipsoid, moderately compressed diaspore with two layer.

Outer layer 9.2 mm long, 6.1 mm wide (N = 1); length to width ratio ~ 1.2 ; layer in uniform thickness of 0.3–0.5 mm surrounding the inner layer, representing 5–10% of full diaspore diameter.

Inner layer isomorphic to the outer layer; 6.7 mm long, 5.7 mm wide (N = 1); irregular, unsmooth surface.

Morphotype JC-R62. UCMP 244430.01.
Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R63

Shape Ellipsoidal

of layers 2

Diaspore type Other

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 1

Descriptions

Ellipsoidal, moderately compressed diaspore with two layer.

Outer layer 7.9 mm long, 4.8 mm wide (N = 1); length to width ratio ~ 1.7 ; layer in uniform thickness of 0.5–0.7 mm, representing 20–30% of the diaspore diameter.

Inner layer ovoidal; 6.3 mm long, 3.8 mm wide (N = 1), irregularly punctate surface.

Morphotype JC-R63. UCMP 244202.01. Scale = 5 mm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R64

Shape Triangularly lenticular

of layers 2

Diaspore type Other

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 1

Descriptions

Lenticular, double-layered diaspore with triangular to obcordate outline; distal emarginate end at $\sim 160^\circ$, proximal point at $\sim 100^\circ$.

Outer layer 12.8 mm long, 20.2 mm wide (N = 1); length to width ratio ~ 0.6 ; 1.5–2.5 mm thick in areas where the layer is preserved.

Inner layer isomorphic to the outer layer; 10.4 mm long, 17.2 mm wide (N = 1); pronounced ridge across the diaspore margin and the median line; surface fibrous.

Morphotype JC-R64. UCMP 244058.01. Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore		Morphotype #	JC-R65
Shape	Obovoidal	# of layers	1
		Diaspore type	Other
Infructescence/compound	<input type="checkbox"/>	# specimens studied	1

Descriptions

Widely obovoidal, minimally compressed diaspore with a single layer; 17.6 mm long, 18.1 mm wide, measured from conservatively extrapolated outline from the bilaterally symmetrical but incompletely preserved specimen; length to width ration ~1; maximum width at ~75% of the full diaspore length; basal 50% with linearly to concavely tapering outline; 7–8 weakly pronounced longitudinal ridges.

Morphotype JC-R65. UCMP 244182.04. Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore		Morphotype #	JC-R66
Shape	Ovoidal	# of layers	2
		Diaspore type	Other
Infructescence/compound	<input type="checkbox"/>	# specimens studied	6

Descriptions

Ovoidal, moderately compressed diaspore with two layers.
 Outer layer 13.4 mm long (N = 6, s.d. = 1.39), 10.6 mm wide (N = 6, s.d. = 0.55); layer of relatively uniform thickness of 1–2 mm, representing 20–25% of the full diaspore diameter; basal area recognized by thickened and slightly protruded region (white arrows).
 Inner layer ovoidal, located centrally; 10.9 mm long (N = 4, s.d. = 1.10), 8.8 mm wide (N = 4, s.d. = 1.05).

Morphotype JC-R66. A) UCMP 244465.01. B) UCMP 244657.01. C) UCMP 244956.01.
 Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R67

Shape Ovoidal/ellipsoidal

of layers 1

Diaspore type Other

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 87

Descriptions

Ovoidal to ellipsoidal, highly compressed diaspore with one layer; 1.5 mm long (N = 87, s.d. = 0.30), 1.0 mm wide (N = 87, s.d. = 0.21); 2–3 surficial ridges present in some specimens; specimens always preserved in a large number together, likely due to unassisted dispersal.

Morphotype JC-R67. A) UCMP 244069.08. B) PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0120.02. C) PMNS-PAL-2021-06-012.05. Scale = 5 mm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore		Morphotype #	JC-R68
Shape	Ovoidal/ellipsoidal	# of layers	1
		Diaspore type	Other
Infructescence/compound	<input type="checkbox"/>	# specimens studied	25

Descriptions

Ovoidal to ellipsoidal, highly compressed diaspores with one layer that are <1 mm in length; 0.54 mm long (N = 25, s.d. = 0.11), 0.38 mm wide (N = 25, s.d.= 0 .08); preserved in a large number in proximity; likely due to unassisted dispersal; some specimens preserved with rootlets, likely representing a large seed bank in soil; more completely preserved specimens were selected for measurement.

cf. JC-R67: The two morphotypes are nearly isometric; yet the dimensions are 1/3–1/2 smaller in the present morphotype.

Remarks. Some specimens are preserved along with specimens of the morphotype JC-R67 (B). It is possible that JC-R67 represent a dehiscent fruit and JC-R68 are dispersed diaspores; however, there are no conclusive evidence supporting this.

Morphotype JC-R68. A) PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0040.01. B) PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0001.06. Scale = 5 mm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore		Morphotype #	JC-R69
Shape	Ovoidal/lacrimoid	# of layers	1
		Diaspore type	Other
Infructescence/compound	<input type="checkbox"/>	# specimens studied	3

Descriptions

Ovoidal to lacrimoid diaspore with one layer; 2.5 mm long (N = 3, s.d. = 0.36), 2.1 mm wide (N = 3, s.d. = 0.17); maximum width occurring at ~35% of the diaspore length; exposed surface shows a centrally raised area.

Morphotype JC-R69. A) UCMP 244852.04. B) PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0347.01. Scale = 1 mm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore		Morphotype #	JC-R70
Shape	Lenticular/discoid	# of layers	2
		Diaspore type	Other
Infructescence/compound	<input type="checkbox"/>	# specimens studied	2

Descriptions

Lenticular to discoid diaspore with convexly trapezoidal outline with two layer.
 Outer layer in convexly trapezoidal with an arcuate distal edge, with an arc of 60–90°;
 3.4 mm long, 3.1 mm wide (N = 2).
 Inner layer discoid with a nearly isomorphic outline to the outer layer; 2.2 mm long, 2.2 mm wide.

Morphotype JC-R70. A) PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0105.01. B) PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0106.01.
 Scale = 5 mm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore		Morphotype #	JC-R71
Shape	Fusiform	# of layers	1
		Diaspore type	Other
Infructescence/compound	<input type="checkbox"/>	# specimens studied	2

Descriptions

Fusiform diaspore with one layer. Diaspore likely fibrous (A) and coriaceous (B); outline convexly tapering towards both ends; 13.6 mm long, 8.1 mm wide (N = 2); length to width ration ~2.

Morphotype JC-R71. A) UCMP 244641.01. B) UCMP 244984.01. Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore		Morphotype #	JC-R72
Shape	Fusiform	# of layers	1
		Diaspore type	Other
Infructescence/compound	<input type="checkbox"/>	# specimens studied	1

Descriptions

Fusiform diaspore with one layer; outline convexly tapering towards both ends; 13.6 mm long, 3.8 mm wide; length to width ratio ~3.5.

Morphotype JC-R72. PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0098.02. Scale = 5 mm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore		Morphotype #	JC-R73
Shape	ellipsoidal	# of layers	1
		Diaspore type	Other
Infructescence/compound	<input type="checkbox"/>	# specimens studied	4

Descriptions

Ellipsoidal to narrowly ovoidal diaspore with a single layer; 2.2 mm long (N = 4, s.d. = 0.19), 1.1 mm wide (N = 4, s.d. = 0.15); a median longitudinal furrow present (A, B).

Morphotype JC-R73. A) UCMP 244166.02. B) UCMP 244264.02. C) UCMP 244166.03. Scale = 1 mm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore		Morphotype #	JC-R74
Shape	Narrowly ovoidal	# of layers	1
		Diaspore type	Other
Infructescence/compound	<input type="checkbox"/>	# specimens studied	4

Descriptions

Narrowly ovoidal diaspore with one layer; 12.5 mm long (N = 4, s.d. = 0.97), 5.3 mm wide (N = 4, s.d. = 0.28); length to width ratio 2.0–2.6; maximum width occurring at 20–30% of the diaspore length; outline linearly to concavely tapering towards distal end.

Morphotype JC-R74. A) UCMP 244980.02. B) UCMP 244354.01. C) UCMP 244076.01. Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R75

Shape: Triangularly lenticular

of layers: 1

Diaspore type: Other

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied: 5

Descriptions

Lenticular diaspore with triangular to broadly ovate outline; all specimens incompletely preserved, with all of them broken off at the median line but the outer layer visible in some specimens (A–C); 7.0 mm long (N = 5, s.d. = 2.09), 5.9 mm wide (N = 5, s.d. = 0.91).

Morphotype JC-R75.

A) UCMP 244983.02.

B) PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0040.02.

C) PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0091.05.

D) UCMP 244354.02.

E) PMNS-PAL-2021-06-0342.03.

Scale = 5 mm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R76

Shape Lenticular

of layers 1

Diaspore type Other

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 1

Descriptions

Lenticular diaspore in a triangular outline with one layer; 21.6 mm long, 18.8 mm wide (N = 1); punctate, roughened surface.

Morphotype JC-R76. UCMP 244464.04. Scale = 1 cm.

Dori's Tuff diaspore

Morphotype #

JC-R77

Shape Ellipsoidal

of layers 1

Diaspore type Other

Infructescence/compound

specimens studied 1

Descriptions

Circularly lenticular diaspore with one layer; diaspore 2.4 mm long, 1.9 mm wide (N = 1); reticulate surficial ridges of irregular polygonal cells; ridges 0.04–0.06 mm wide; irregular cells 0.3–0.7 mm long, 0.2–0.4 mm wide; marginal cells more elongated.

Morphotype JC-R77. UCMP 244882.04. Scale = 1 mm.